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Computational Fluid Dynamics Analysis of Wind Turbine for Different Tilt Angles

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ABSTRACT

Energy consumption and environmental degradation due to conventional fuel consumption is important criteria for researchers in the world. The solar and wind energy are abundantly available which can be used day and night time in different part of the earth. The attention is made on wind power production in rural and urban areas along with wind farms. It is found that multi rotor wind plants are superior over single rotor. In the current study, attention is focused on small wind power plants for different tilt angles. CFD simulations are carried out on NACA 5510 airfoil blade to test rotational speed performance of horizontal axis wind turbine (HAWT) with wind velocity varying from 3 m/s to 7 m/s for tilt angles from 0° to 18° . It is found that for wind velocity of 3 m/s, blade velocity is 16.52 m/s at root tip. It is observed that pressure and velocity values are reduced at 18° tilt angles as compared to 0° while aerodynamic performance is optimum at blade tilt angle of 4° . The path lines and velocity contours are studied for different tilt angles with wind velocity. The

power obtained from CFD analysis is validated with theoretical values using Burton's theory. It is investigated that all the results obtained for torque and power generated along the length of blade are within $\pm 5\%$ for theoretical and CFD. These results are very useful for further design of wind turbine blades.

Keywords: HAWT, wind energy, tilt angle, multi rotor, CFD

Nomenclature:

A	Area (m ²)
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
C _p	Power coefficient
d	Diameter of blade (m)
HAWT	Horizontal axis wind turbine
k	Turbulence kinetic energy (J)
NACA	National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
P	Power in the wind (W)
p	Pressure (N/m ²)
T	Torque (Nm)
v	Average wind speed (m/s)
VAWT	Vertical Axis Wind Turbine
ω	Angular velocity (rad/sec)
ρ	Density (kg/m ³)
θ	Tilt angle (°)

1. INTRODUCTION

The high-grade energy consumption is increasing with the standard of living in the world. The fossil fuels are depleting fast due to limited sources of coal and oil. The researchers are focusing attention on the renewable energy sources such as wind and solar which are synchronous in nature. The energy from the sun is harnessed in day time whereas wind could provide energy throughout day and night time. The small scale wind turbines are used in residential purposes which covers large population whereas big turbines are useful in commercial applications. Thus, in the research, focus is on the smaller wind turbines. The optimum design of turbine blade is important for power generation with reduced vibrations and stability. The wind energy produced from horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWT) blades is more than vertical axis wind turbines (VAWT) blades due to entire area swept by HAWT blades. Large-scale HAWTs are useful in wind farms/off-shore areas whereas small scale HAWTs are normally used in household applications. HAWT are classified as micro scale (d = 0.1 m), small scale (d = 0.1 to 1 m), mid-scale (d = 1 m to 5 m) and large scale (d = 5 m to 45 m). HAWT systems are operated at constant or variable speed depending on generator. Figure 1 shows components of HAWT such as rotor, drive train, pitch control system, generator, and electronic control system. All wind turbines use rotors with blades and hub for conversion of kinetic energy in wind into mechanical energy at

rotating shaft by conversion of aerodynamic forces into positive torque on the blades.

Figure 1. Components of HAWT

The use of renewable energy harnessing is increasing in the modern world with the use technology and resources but there are few challenges for efficiency and power output (Raghuwanshi et al.,2019). The main objective in the wind turbine optimization is power generated by wind turbine with wind turbine tilt angle that affects shear force and bending moment at tower top and blade root which affected aerodynamic performance of wind turbine (Pao et al.,2009). Zhao et al. (2018) proposed new method to control wind turbine. They found that as tilt angle increases, wind speed increases with reduced blade loading with shear force at top and bottom of tower. Kim et al. (2011) researched on the interaction between blade and tower with nonlinear vortex correction method. They found that as the yaw angle and wind shear exponent increases, interaction between blade and tower decreases. Some investigated CFD performance of blade tower interaction with influence of tower on total aerodynamic performance of wind turbine(Wang et al.,2012). Narayana et al. (2000) studied gyroscopic effect of small scale wind turbines. They investigated that the tilt angle alteration can improve aerodynamic performance of small-scale wind turbines. Zhao et al. (2017) studied the structural performance of two blade wind turbine at various tilt angles. Pao et al. (2009) studied advanced controllers in wind turbine farms related modeling and control methods. Choi et al. (2014) observed aerodynamic power output change of wind turbines with inter-turbine spacing with CFD for tower and nacelle. They studied CFD analysis for different parameters such as aerodynamic power output, wind velocity change, pressure drop across wind turbine rotor with wind speed deficit due to wake effect. Zhao et al. (2018) investigated structural dynamics for two bladed wind turbine configurations for tilt control with Computational Structural Dynamics (CSD) analysis for nacelle tilt angles varying from 5°, 20°, 35°, 50° and 65° and yaw angles with 20°, 30°, 40°, 50° and 60° respectively. They found that the tower top and base shear forces were reduced significantly with nacelle tilt control compared with yaw control. Wang et al. (2019) studied two-dimensional wind speed model with modified tower shadow and wind shear models for different tilt angles. They found that the tilt angle reduced, effect of periodic disturbances on aerodynamic power fluctuation. Annoni et al. (2017) studied feasibility of tilt in wind power plant for two and three turbine arrays and found that three-turbine array produces more power.

Onel et al. (2020) studied large eddy solver based Open FOAM software coupled with actuator line model for CFD simulation of wind turbines to estimate power generation and validated with yawed tandem wind turbines for 5 MW capacity. They performed simulations for upstream and the downstream turbines for power estimation. They investigated performance of yawed upstream rotor on its wake deflection and power generation with respect to tandem configuration. They investigated that coupled solver was better for capturing wake deficits and wake deflections for power generation of tandem wind turbine. Wang et al. (2020) studied aerodynamic performance of wind turbine at different tilt angles with STAR CCM+ for various performance parameters such as thrust, power, lift and drag on airfoil for various angle of attack. They investigated effect of wind shear exponents and turbulence intensity on wind turbine power generation. Sarkar et al. (2012) performed experimental observation for 1 kW power capacity with 11 m/s and 1 m diameter wind turbine for turbine power output and efficiency with different tip speed ratios and validated results with simulation. Vermeer et al. (2003) performed experimental study of aerodynamics of HAWT to find wake region properties behind turbine blade. Trigaux et al. (2020) studied tilted wake deviation in wind farms using CFD large eddy simulation with increase in power output from the wind. Santo et al. (2020) studied analysis of rotor and tower interaction with effects of rotor's tilt angle of 5° and yaw misalignment on HAWT. The tilt leads to consistently larger tip deflections, because of arising gravitational load in axial direction. Wang et al. (2020) investigated aerodynamic performance in terms of thrust, power, drag and lift of blade of wind turbine at different tilt angles varying from 0° to 12° with STAR CCM+ CFD and concluded the best performance of wind turbine is at tilt angle of 4° . Johlas (2021) concluded that large rotor tilt angles steer wakes in downward and creates short wider wakes.

2. Material and Methods

In research work, main intention is to study comparative performance of wind flow in normal and tilted rotor for different wind velocities using micro wind turbine. The parameters such as torque, velocity, temperature, and pressure counters across the blade are studied with ANSYS CFD with flow visualization in terms of path lines, stream lines, streak lines and wake region eddy formation. The model is formed with proper initialization, mesh generation, solver controls and post processing for different performance parameters. Figure 2 is blade airfoil (NACA 5510) HAWT with diameter 600 mm. Figure 3 shows moving reference frame over wind turbine blades while Figure 4 is presenting boundary conditions with inlet, outlet, and wall.

Figure 2. Turbine blades

Figure 3. Moving reference frame over wind turbine blades

Figure 4. Boundary conditions

Hybrid (Hexahedral and Tetrahedral) mesh is created using ICEM CFD with Tri-Tet mesh in rotating domain (Quick method) and Hexahedral (Blocking method) mesh in main domain. Maximum element (mesh) size is 100 mm (main domain) and minimum element (mesh) size is 1.5 mm (blade) with two million total number of cells including tetrahedral 18,00000 and hexahedral 2,00000. The mesh orthogonal quality is 0.15. The boundary conditions given are velocity inlet varying from 3 m/s to 7 m/s, pressure outlet as atmospheric with adiabatic wall. Figure 5 shows hexahedral grid on main domain and sectional view of domain. Figure 6 shows enlarged view of rotating domain section.

Figure 5. Hexahedral grid on main domain and sectional view of domain

Figure 6. Enlarged view of rotating domain section

3. Results and Discussion

The power generated by the wind turbine is calculated using Equation 1.

$$P = 0.5 \times \rho \times C_p \times A \times V^3 \quad (1)$$

Where:

P = Power in the wind (W/m²)

ρ = Air density (kg/m³), (1.2 kg/m³ at 200 °C at sea level)

A = Projected wind turbine rotor area (m²)

v = Average wind speed (m/s)

C_p = Power coefficient which is a function of both tip speed ratio and blade pitch angle

Power coefficient (C_p) is ratio of output power produced to the power available in the wind.

$$P = T \times \omega \quad (2)$$

Where T is torque in N-m and ω is the angular speed in radian/sec.

In CFD solution solver parameters are selected such as pressure-based solver, steady state condition, Turbulence model (k- ω) SST, solution method as second order upwind, residual convergence of 0.001, monitoring drag and lift coefficient of blade with conservation of mass, momentum, and energy. Figure 7 shows contours of blade velocity from front at 0° tilt angle. It is observed that velocity increases from center to tip of blade. The blade tip is important while designing the blades from centrifugal force and stress point of view.

Figure 7. Contour of blade velocity from front at 0° and 18° tilt angles

Figure 8. Contour of blade pressure from front at 0° and 18° tilt angles

Figure 9. Velocity along the blade at 0° tilt angle

Figure 10. Velocity along the blade at 18° tilt angle

Figure 11. Pressure along the blade at 18° tilt angle

Blade tip speed is calculated theoretically and compared with CFD in Table 1.

Table 1 Blade tip speed

N(rpm)	Tip speed(m/s)	Tip Speed from CFD (m/s)
478	15	16.50
637	20	22.01
796	25	27.52
955	30	33.03
1115	35	38.53

Table 2 Blade speed at different wind velocities

Wind Velocity (m/s)	N0	N18
3	478	447

5	796	736
7	1115	1047

Table 3 CFD results for torque at different wind velocities at 0° and 18° tilt angle

Wind Velocity (m/s)	Torque(N-m) at 0° tilt angle	Torque (N-m) at 18° tilt angle
3	24.7655	22.23
5	75.91	69.47
7	155.203	137.76

Table 4 Power at 0° and 18° tilt angles for different wind velocities

Wind Velocity (m/s)	Power, P ₀ (W)	Power, P ₁₈ (W)	Power, CFD P ₁₈ =P ₀ cos ³ 18 (W)
3	1.239	1.04	1.0531
5	6.3244	5.3515	5.3757
7	18.1127	15.0965	15.3958

The velocity measurements recorded on the surface of a wind turbine blade are essential for comprehending and enhancing the aerodynamic efficacy of the turbine. Such measurements offer valuable information regarding the flow dynamics surrounding the blades, which has a direct impact on the turbine’s efficiency and energy generation. Through the examination of velocity distributions, engineers are able to pinpoint regions that may benefit from enhancements in blade design and functionality. Investigating the speed on the blade's surface aids in gaining a thorough comprehension of the boundary layer traits, vital for the aerodynamic performance enhancement in wind turbines. Variations in the boundary layer flow dynamics greatly affect the lift and drag forces on the blades, subsequently influencing the turbine's efficiency (Maeda et al., 2014 ; Horia et al., 2010). The pattern of velocity across the blade functions as a signal for the presence of vortices and the onset of flow separation, both fundamental for analyzing the aerodynamic stability and efficiency of the turbine (Sanda & Dimitrie, 2014). For instance, studies using computational simulations have indicated that the force of vortices grows alongside wind speed, consequently affecting the aerodynamic efficiency of blades. Comprehending the velocity distribution along the blade surface is likewise crucial for evaluating the structural integrity of wind turbines (Sanda & Dimitrie, 2014). Velocity data can help in predicting and mitigating the effects of dynamic loads on the blades. So velocity values on the blade surface can be considered instrumental in enhancing wind turbine performance.

The measurement of pressure values on the blade surface of a wind turbine is crucial for comprehending and refining the aerodynamic performance of the turbine. This data offers valuable insights into the aerodynamic forces exerted on the blades, which are vital for enhancing efficiency, identifying operational challenges, and advancing the design of wind turbines. Understanding how pressure varies on the blade surface is fundamental in establishing important aerodynamic

characteristics including lift, drag, and angle of attack, which are essential for ensuring the turbine operates effectively and remains stable.

Thus values of velocity, pressure and tip speed and their variation obtained in the CFD studies will be very useful for further studies of researchers.

4. Conclusions

The current research work is performed with the objective of demonstrating the behavior of wind at different tilt angles. Simulations are carried out on NACA 5510 airfoil blade to test rotational speed performance of HAWT with wind speed varying from 3 m/s to 7 m/s for tilt angle varying from 0° to 18° . It is observed that velocity and pressure along the length of blade are increasing from root to tip. It is found that for wind velocity of 3 m/s, blade velocity is 16.52 m/s at root tip. It is investigated that all the results for torque and power generated for blade at various points are within $\pm 5\%$ for theoretical and CFD. It is observed that pressure and velocity values are reduced at 18° tilt angle as compared to 0° tilt angle at the same point while path lines and velocity contours demonstrated the effect of tilting turbine blades. The power obtained from the CFD analysis is following the same trend as calculated using Burton's theory. Thus, the current study is useful to study and develop turbine blades and multi rotor wind turbines for power generation from small turbine power plants.

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